

To Nieve
by Brian Paul Kaess

Regina brought me Nieve one cold November night,
A darling white kitten, so hungry and full of fright,
She was born from her cat mummy's litter in San Jose de Ramos,
Up to this point in life, she was nothing but blameless,
It was frigid, so she cuddled up close and dear,
I covered her with my blanket and provided some cheer,
I should've said, 'Nieve! Nieve! You've found your forever home!'
But all she wanted shortly thereafter was to roam,
Exploring her surroundings inside and out,
She was so adorable, she began to gain clout,
Among our cats Baby & Candy, she rose up in the Pride,
There was no turning back now, no turning the tide,
So keen she was to be fed from the hand,
She raced to the dinner table to make her demand,
I fed her extras, as much as I could,
For there was little doubt to my conscience whether I should,
She sipped milk, ate chick-breast fillet, and gobbled human food galore,
With spicy, beef chow mein, & roasted ham, she tried some more!
Her stomach was indeed the bottomless pit,
Matching her Master in appetite and wit,
Eventually, Nieve, Sabrina & Candy became friends,
Spending many a Summer night slumbered on my bed,
Nieve's fur was snow-white as a Dove,
But nothing was more pure than her abiding Love,
A furry friend who shared the common meal with the rest,
She was of course our very special guest,
She loved to adorn herself across the Love Seat upstairs,
It was only upon this narrow seat, she would never sleep in pairs,
Nieve almost died on me one day,
But I revived her with 'laying hands' - that kept her from turning grey,
So Nieve was the best there ever was,
She was happy just to touch me with her gentle paws.